

Testing Language Communicative Competence - An Overview

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ABSTRACT:

Language learning/teaching is considered a continuous process. To maintain the continuity, a teacher needs to frequently assess learners' achievement and proficiency that he/she has attained during the 'learning process,' rather than after the lesson process is completed. Language teachers who consider language learning a continuous process stress that evaluation/testing is a continuous process, simultaneous with the lesson process.

However, it must be pointed out that language testing has not kept pace with the developments in the language teaching, and applied linguistics has done very little in this area. It is true that any language teaching techniques can be used for language testing. A traditional dictation task, translation work, reading assignment, any question-answer technique, an oral test and a close- test that uses the fill-in-the-gaps technique used for evaluation can become a language test. Davies (1968) once wrote, "a good test is an obedient servant since it follows and apes the teaching". Most of the language tests that are used are surface tests which test only surface problems in language. In such tests, the learners are asked to supply the correct forms as fill-in-the-blank types, spelling, etc. Often, even the surface tests are used only to supply what is given in the text. These text-based language tests evaluate only learner's ability to recall what they memorize; and hence, they are reproductive in nature. Outside the text, people speak, listen, read, write, think, compose, describe, pray, promise and do meaning processing in order to achieve certain life-oriented goals and negotiate meaning as realized in pain and pleasure. Language testing in the communicative approach can open up a number of possibilities that are literally unlimited.

KEY WORDS: Language Learning, Language Teaching, Proficiency, Learning Process

INTRODUCTION

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However, testing language has traditionally taken the form of testing knowledge about language—usually the testing of knowledge of vocabulary and grammar. Hymes (1971) proposes the concept of communicative competence, which refers to the ability to exchange information in a foreign language with native speakers of the language. He argued that a speaker can produce grammatical sentences that are completely inappropriate. In communicative competence, he included not only the ability to form correct sentences but also the ability to use them at appropriate times. Since Hymes proposed the idea in the early 70s, it

has been expanded considerably and various types of competencies have been proposed. However, the basic idea underlying communicative competence is the ability to use the language appropriately, both receptively and productively, in real situation.

AN OVERVIEW OF A TEST

During the phase of structural linguistics, language was analyzed at several levels and into several components. Three levels of language analysis that were recognized are Expression, Form and Content of language. Based on this approach, the evaluation technique then recommended was the well known Discreet Point Evaluation technique. Carroll (1980) first named it Discreet Point as opposed to the tests of integrative skills. With the developments in the linguistics theories and approaches to language analysis, one finds that the structural grammar was replaced by Chomsky's (1966) Transformational Generative Grammar. And we are familiar with the reactions against his rather restricted views of 'competence'. Most of these reactions were primarily due to his argument to analyze language in isolation from its socio-cultural matrix. Objecting to Chomsky's notion of 'competence,' Halliday (1973) proposed a socio-semantic approach to language analysis, which includes the rules for use of language in appropriate context. With these developments in the field of linguistic theories and description, there are changes in approach to language teaching/learning process and testing theories.

Types of Test

Not all language tests are of the same kind. They differ with how they are designed, and what is the method and purpose of the test.

Discrete point tests

Early theories of test performance, influenced by structuralist linguistics, saw knowledge of language as consisting of mastery of the features of the language as a system. This position was clearly articulated by Robert Lado (1961). His testing theory focused on the learner's knowledge of the grammatical system, vocabulary and aspects of pronunciation. There was a tendency to atomize and decontextualize the knowledge to be tested and to test the aspects

of knowledge in isolation. This practice of testing separate individual points of knowledge is known as discrete testing. The nature of discrete testing is objective.

Integrative test

After some decades, the necessity of evaluating the practical language skills of foreign students wishing to study in universities in abroad or to get employment in corporate sectors poised assessing the productive capacities of language. It focused on the integrated performance of the language user. The discrete point tradition of testing was seen as focusing too exclusively on the knowledge of the formal linguistic system for its own sake rather than on the way such knowledge is used to achieve communication. The new orientation resulted in the development of such tests that integrated knowledge of relevant systematic features of language with an understanding of context. This integrative test requires the candidate to combine many language elements in the completion of a task. This might involve writing a composition, making notes while listening to a lecture, taking a dictation, or completing close passage. But the problem with such integrative tests was that they tended to be expensive as they were time consuming and difficult to score (McNamara 2000). This also required trained raters and, sometimes, was potentially unreliable

Pragmatic tests

Research carried out by John Oiler (1971) in the 1970s seemed to offer a solution. The major traits of pragmatic tests are as follows:

- *They require the learner to use language as in real-life context.*
- *The learner is required to process the meaning of discourse within a period of time which we would normally take in real life.*
- *They are integrative and adopt a holistic approach to language. However, it does not follow that all integrative tests are pragmatic.*

Oiler argued that certain kinds of more economical and efficient tests, particularly the close test (gap-filling reading tests), measured the same kind of skills as those

tested in productive tests. Such tests were easy to construct, relatively easy to score, based on a compelling theory of language use, and expensive tests of the productive skills of speaking and writing. Thus, the cloze became very popular form of test in the 1970s and 1980s. Unfortunately, further work soon showed that cloze tests on the whole seemed mostly to be measuring the same kind of things as discrete point tests of grammar and vocabulary. It seems that there are no short cuts in the testing of communicative skills.

COMPUTERS AND LANGUAGE TESTING

Rapid developments in computer technology have exerted a major impact on test delivery. Many important national and international language tests like NELTS, TOEFL and IELTS are moving to Computer Based Testing (CBT). Stimulus texts and prompts are presented not in examination booklets but on the screen, with candidates being required to key in their responses. The advent of CBT, however, has not necessarily involved any change in test content, remaining quite conservative in its assumptions, but often simply represents a change in the methods of testing. However, there are limitations and advantages of computer testing, especially productive skills which represent the social character of a language.

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